

p -ADIC VALUATION OF $\prod_{k=m+1}^n (k^2 - m^2)$

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Abstract

This paper presents the p -adic valuation of the sequence $C_n(m) = \prod_{k=m+1}^n (k^2 - m^2)$, $n = m + 1, m + 2, \dots$. An explicit formula is derived for the p -adic valuation of $C_n(m)$. From an applicational perspective, this study proves that $C_n(m)$ is not a square when $m = 2, 3$. Additionally, this paper provides a criterion for $C_n(m)$ being a powerful number when $n \geq 3m$.

1. Introduction

Let $f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Squares and powerful numbers in the sequence $C_n(f) = \prod_{k=1}^n f(k)$ have already attracted significant attention of several researchers.

In 2008, Amdeberhan, Medina, and Moll [1] presented a conjecture that $C_n(f)$ is not a square when $f(x) = x^2 + 1$ and $n > 3$. After the conjecture was proven by Cilleruelo [3], the problems related to the squares in $C_n(f)$ have been studied by numerous mathematicians.

For $f(x) = x^2 + b$ with $b \in \mathbb{Z}$, Ho [10], Hong and Liu [11], Gürel [8], and Zhang and Niu [16] studied the cases $b = 1, b = -1, b = m^2 - 1$, and $b = m^2$, respectively. Fang [7] proved that $C_n(f)$ is not a square when $f(x) = 4x^2 + 1$ and $2x^2 - 2x + 1$. Yang, Togbé, and He [14] studied the number of squares in the sequence $C_n(f)$, where $f(x) = ax^2 + b$ with $(a, b) = 1, 1 \leq a \leq 10$, and $1 \leq b \leq 20$.

Additionally, the squares in $C_n(f)$ when the degree of $f(x)$ is greater than 2 have been investigated. For $f(x) = x^3 + 1$, Gürel and Kisisel [9] proved that $C_n(f)$ is

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not a square. Generally, for irreducible $f(x)$, the number of squares in the sequence $C_n(f)$ was estimated by Cilleruelo, Luca, Quirós, and Shparlinski [4].

For $f(x) = x^d + 1$, Zhang and Wang [18], Chen and Gong [6], and Chen, Gong, and Ren [5] discussed the cases where d is a prime number greater than 5, an odd prime, and an odd number, respectively, to study powerful numbers in $C_n(f)$. When $f(x) = x^d + q^d$, Niu and Liu [12] and Yang and Zhao [15] investigated the cases where $d = 3$ and d is an odd integer, respectively.

Now, for $C_n(m) = \prod_{k=m+1}^n (k^2 - m^2)$, we discuss the p -adic valuations of $C_n(m)$ in this study and extend results for $C_n(1)$ by Hong and Liu [11].

For a prime p , let $v_p(n) = e$ if $p^e \mid n$ and $p^{e+1} \nmid n$. Let $\sum_{i=0}^l n_i p^i$ be the p -adic expansion of n . Then, we write $s_p(n) = \sum_{i=0}^l n_i$.

For positive integers x and y , with $x \geq y$, we can define a constant $\delta_p(x, y)$ as follows. Let

$$x = a_0 + a_1p + a_2p^2 + \cdots + a_l p^l \tag{1}$$

and

$$y = b_0 + b_1p + b_2p^2 + \cdots + b_k p^k \tag{2}$$

be the p -adic expansions of x and y , respectively. For convenience, let $b_i = 0$ if $i > k$. Define

$$I = \{i \mid a_i - b_i < 0, i = 0, 1, \dots, l\} \cup \{i_0\} = \{i_0, i_1, i_2, \dots, i_t\}, \tag{3}$$

$$J = \{j \mid a_j - b_j > 0, j = 0, 1, \dots, l\} \cup \{j_0\} = \{j_0, j_1, j_2, \dots, j_s\}, \tag{4}$$

where $i_0 = j_0 = -1$, $i_1 < i_2 < \cdots < i_t$, and $j_1 < j_2 < \cdots < j_s$. Then $x - y$ can be written as

$$x - y = \sum_{r=1}^t (a_{i_r} - b_{i_r})p^{i_r} + \sum_{r=1}^s (a_{j_r} - b_{j_r})p^{j_r}.$$

Let

$$I' = \{i_k \in I \mid i_{k-1} \leq j < i_k \text{ for some } j \in J\} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{h_1}\} \tag{5}$$

and

$$J' = \{j_k \in J \mid j_{k-1} < i < j_k \text{ for some } i \in I\} = \{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{h_2}\}, \tag{6}$$

where $\alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \cdots < \alpha_{h_1}$ and $\beta_1 < \beta_2 < \cdots < \beta_{h_2}$.

Definition 1. For positive integers $x \geq y$ and with the same notation as in Equations (5) and (6), we define

$$\delta_p(x, y) = \sum_{j \in J'} j - \sum_{i \in I'} i.$$

In this paper, we show the following results.

Theorem 1. *Let x, y be positive integers with $x \geq y$. We have*

$$s_p(x - y) + s_p(y) - s_p(x) = (p - 1)\delta_p(x, y).$$

By Theorem 1, the p -adic valuation of the binomial coefficient $\binom{x}{y}$ is just $\delta_p(x, y)$.

Corollary 1. *Let x, y be positive integers with $x \geq y$. We have*

$$v_p\left(\binom{x}{y}\right) = \delta_p(x, y).$$

By Theorem 1, a formula of $v_p(C_n(m))$ can be formulated, and the asymptotic behavior of $v_p(C_n(m))$ can be studied.

Theorem 2. *Let m, n be positive integers with $n \geq m + 1$. We have*

$$v_p(C_n(m)) = \frac{2}{p - 1}(n - m - s_p(n - m)) + \delta_p(n + m, 2m).$$

Corollary 2. *For any prime p , we have $v_p(C_n(m)) \sim \frac{2n}{p-1}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.*

Hence, we deduce the following corollary.

Corollary 3. *Let m, n be positive integers with $n \geq m + 1$. Then $C_n(m)$ is a square if and only if $\delta_p(n + m, 2m)$ is even for any prime p .*

From the applicational perspective of Theorem 2, when $m = 2$ or $m = 3$, we can show that a prime p always exists such that $v_p(C_n(m))$ is odd. Consequently, we can deduce the following theorems.

Theorem 3. *When $m = 2$, we have that $C_n(2)$ is not a square if $n \geq 3$.*

Theorem 4. *When $m = 3$, we have that $C_n(3)$ is not a square if $n \geq 4$.*

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we study the properties of $\delta_p(x, y)$ and prove Theorems 1 and 2. A comparative study of our formula for $v_p(C_n(1))$ relative to that of [11] is presented in Section 3. In Sections 4 and 5, we restrict our attention to $m = 2$ and $m = 3$ and prove Theorems 3 and 4, respectively. Finally, a criterion for $C_n(m)$ being a powerful number when $n \geq 3m$ is discussed in Section 6.

2. Proofs of Theorems 1 and 2

Recall the definition of $\delta_p(x, y)$. The following two examples contribute to our understanding of $I', J', \delta_p(x, y)$, and Theorem 2.

Example 1. Let $p = 17$,

$$x = 2 + 17 + 4 \cdot 17^2 + 2 \cdot 17^3 + 3 \cdot 17^4,$$

and

$$y = 1 + 2 \cdot 17 + 17^2 + 2 \cdot 17^4.$$

Thus,

$$x - y = 1 + (-1) \cdot 17 + 3 \cdot 17^2 + 2 \cdot 17^3 + 17^4.$$

We have $I = \{-1, 1\}$, $J = \{-1, 0, 2, 3, 4\}$, $I' = \{1\}$, and $J' = \{2\}$, which results in $\delta_{17}(x, y) = 1$. Let $x = n + m$ and $y = 2m$. It follows that $n = 177881$, $m = 83683$, and

$$n - m = 94198 = 1 + 16 \cdot 17 + 2 \cdot 17^2 + 2 \cdot 17^3 + 17^4.$$

By Theorem 2, we have $v_{17}(C_n(m)) = 11773$.

Example 2. Let $p = 7$,

$$x = 1 + 3 \cdot 7 + 2 \cdot 7^2 + 6 \cdot 7^3 + 4 \cdot 7^4 + 4 \cdot 7^5 + 7^6 + 2 \cdot 7^7 + 4 \cdot 7^8 + 6 \cdot 7^9 + 7^{10},$$

and

$$y = 3 + 7 + 4 \cdot 7^2 + 3 \cdot 7^3 + 2 \cdot 7^4 + 6 \cdot 7^5 + 2 \cdot 7^6 + 4 \cdot 7^7 + 4 \cdot 7^8 + 3 \cdot 7^9.$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} x - y &= -2 + 2 \cdot 7 + (-2) \cdot 7^2 + 3 \cdot 7^3 + 2 \cdot 7^4 + (-2) \cdot 7^5 \\ &\quad + (-1) \cdot 7^6 + (-2) \cdot 7^7 + 3 \cdot 7^9 + 7^{10}. \end{aligned}$$

We have $I = \{-1, 0, 2, 5, 6, 7\}$, $J = \{-1, 1, 3, 4, 9\}$, $I' = \{0, 2, 5\}$, and $J' = \{1, 3, 9\}$, which results in $\delta_7(x, y) = 6$. Let $x = n + m$ and $y = 2m$. It follows that $n = 475621653$, $m = 73878187$, and

$$\begin{aligned} n - m &= 401743466 \\ &= 5 + 7 + 5 \cdot 7^2 + 2 \cdot 7^3 + 2 \cdot 7^4 + 5 \cdot 7^5 \\ &\quad + 5 \cdot 7^6 + 4 \cdot 7^7 + 6 \cdot 7^8 + 2 \cdot 7^9 + 7^{10}. \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 2, we have $v_7(C_n(m)) = 133914476$.

Lemma 1. *Considering the same notation as was used in Equations (3), (4), (5), and (6), we have that $\alpha_1 = i_1$, that α_k is the smallest element in I and is greater than β_{k-1} for $k \geq 2$, and that β_k is the smallest element in J and is greater than α_k for $k \geq 1$. As an immediate consequence, we have $h_1 = h_2$.*

Proof. Since $i_1 > i_0$ and $i_0 = j_0 < i_1$, we have $i_1 \in I'$. Hence $\alpha_1 = i_1$.

If $\beta_1 = j_{s_1}$, we claim that $i_1 \in (j_{s_1-1}, j_{s_1})$. Otherwise, we have $i_1 < j_{s_1-1}$. It follows that $s_1 > 1$. Therefore, there exists $j_{s'_1} \in J$ such that $j_{s'_1} \leq j_{s_1-1} < j_{s_1}$ and $j_{s'_1-1} < i_1 < j_{s'_1}$. Thus $j_{s'_1} \in J'$, which contradicts $j_{s_1} = \beta_1$. Hence j_{s_1} is the smallest element in J and is greater than i_1 .

If $\alpha_2 = i_{t_2} > i_1$, we claim that $\beta_1 \in (i_{t_2-1}, i_{t_2})$. Otherwise, there exists $i_{t'_2} \in I$ such that $i_{t'_2} \leq i_{t_2-1} < i_{t_2}$ and $i_{t'_2-1} < \beta_1 < i_{t'_2}$. It follows that $i_{t'_2} \in I'$ and $i_{t'_2} > i_1$, which contradicts $i_{t_2} = \alpha_2$. Thus, from $\beta_1 \in (i_{t_2-1}, i_{t_2})$, we have i_{t_2} is the smallest element in I that is greater than β_1 .

Therefore, the lemma follows by induction. □

Definition 2. For a positive integer n and a prime p , if

$$n = n_0 + n_1p + n_2p^2 + \dots + n_l p^l, \tag{7}$$

where $0 < n_l \leq p - 1$ and $1 - p \leq n_i \leq p - 1$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, l - 1$, we can define

$$(n)_\Gamma = \sum_{i \in \Gamma \cap \mathbb{Z}} n_i p^i,$$

where $\Gamma \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ is an interval.

Lemma 2. *Considering the same notation as was used in Definition 2, we have*

$$s_p(n) = s_p((n)_{[0,t]}) + s_p((n)_{(t,l]}),$$

where $t = \min\{i \mid n_i > 0, i = 0, 1, \dots, l\}$.

Proof. Since $n_t, n_l > 0$, it follows that $(n)_{[0,t]}$ and $(n)_{(t,l]}$ are both positive. Then

$$(n)_{[0,t]} = n'_0 + n'_1 p + \dots + n'_t p^t \tag{8}$$

and

$$(n)_{(t,l]} = n'_{t+1} p^{t+1} + n'_{t+2} p^{t+2} + \dots + n'_l p^l, \tag{9}$$

where $0 \leq n'_i \leq p - 1$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, l$. Thus

$$s_p((n)_{[0,t]}) = n'_0 + n'_1 + \dots + n'_t,$$

and

$$s_p((n)_{(t,l]}) = n'_{t+1} + n'_{t+2} + \dots + n'_l.$$

From Equations (8) and (9), we have

$$n = (n)_{[0,t]} + (n)_{(t,l]} = n'_0 + n'_1 p + \dots + n'_l p^l.$$

It follows that

$$s_p(n) = n'_0 + n'_1 + \cdots + n'_l = s_p((n)_{[0,t]}) + s_p((n)_{(t,l]}).$$

□

Lemma 3. *Let n be a positive integer. If*

$$n = n_0 + n_1p + \cdots + n_l p^l$$

with $0 < n_i \leq p - 1$ and $1 - p \leq n_i \leq 0$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, l - 1$, we have

$$s_p(n) = \sum_{i=0}^l n_i + (p - 1)(l - k),$$

where $k = \min\{i \mid n_i \neq 0, i = 0, 1, \dots, l\}$.

Proof. Write

$$n = n_{i_1}p^{i_1} + n_{i_2}p^{i_2} + \cdots + n_{i_t}p^{i_t} + n_l p^l,$$

where $n_i < 0$ for $i = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_t$ and $i_1 < i_2 < \cdots < i_t$, then the p -adic expansion of n is

$$\begin{aligned} n &= (n_{i_1} + p)p^{i_1} + (p - 1)p^{i_1+1} + \cdots + (p - 1)p^{i_2-1} + (n_{i_2} + p - 1)p^{i_2} \\ &\quad + (p - 1)p^{i_2+1} + \cdots + (p - 1)p^{i_3-1} + (n_{i_3} + p - 1)p^{i_3} \\ &\quad + \cdots \\ &\quad + (n_{i_t} + p - 1)p^{i_t} + (p - 1)p^{i_t+1} + \cdots + (p - 1)p^{l-1} + (n_l - 1)p^l. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$s_p(n) = \sum_{i=0}^l n_i + (p - 1)(l - i_1) = \sum_{i=0}^l n_i + (p - 1)(l - k).$$

□

Corollary 4. *For positive integers $x \geq y$, and with the same notation as in Equations (5) and (6), when $k = 1, 2, \dots, h_1$, we have*

$$s_p((x - y)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) + s_p((y)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) - s_p((x)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) = (p - 1)(\beta_k - \alpha_k).$$

Proof. Observe that $1 - p \leq a_i - b_i \leq 0$ for $i \in [\alpha_k, \beta_k]$, $1 - p \leq a_{\alpha_k} - b_{\alpha_k} < 0$, and $0 < a_{\beta_k} - b_{\beta_k} \leq p - 1$. By Lemma 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} s_p((x - y)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) &= \sum_{i \in [\alpha_k, \beta_k]} (a_i - b_i) + (p - 1)(\beta_k - \alpha_k) \\ &= s_p((x)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) - s_p((y)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) + (p - 1)(\beta_k - \alpha_k). \end{aligned}$$

□

Proof of Theorem 1. By Lemma 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & s_p(x - y) + s_p(y) - s_p(x) \\
 &= s_p((x - y)_{[0, \alpha_1]}) + s_p((y)_{[0, \alpha_1]}) - s_p((x)_{[0, \alpha_1]}) \\
 &+ \sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \left(s_p((x - y)_{(\beta_k, \alpha_{k+1})}) + s_p((y)_{(\beta_k, \alpha_{k+1})}) - s_p((x)_{(\beta_k, \alpha_{k+1})}) \right) \\
 &+ \sum_{k=1}^h \left(s_p((x - y)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) + s_p((y)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) - s_p((x)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) \right) \\
 &+ s_p((x - y)_{(\beta_{h_1}, l]}) + s_p((y)_{(\beta_{h_1}, l]}) - s_p((x)_{(\beta_{h_1}, l]}). \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

If $i \in [0, \alpha_1)$, then $a_i - b_i \geq 0$. Thus, the p -adic expansion of $(x - y)_{[0, \alpha_1]}$ is $\sum_{i \in [0, \alpha_1)} (a_i - b_i)p^i$. Therefore

$$s_p((x - y)_{[0, \alpha_1]}) = \sum_{i \in [0, \alpha_1)} (a_i - b_i) = s_p((x)_{[0, \alpha_1]}) - s_p((y)_{[0, \alpha_1]}).$$

Hence, we have

$$s_p((x - y)_{[0, \alpha_1]}) + s_p((y)_{[0, \alpha_1]}) - s_p((x)_{[0, \alpha_1]}) = 0.$$

Additionally, by similar arguments we have

$$s_p((x - y)_{[\beta_{h_1+1}, l]}) + s_p((y)_{[\beta_{h_1+1}, l]}) - s_p((x)_{[\beta_{h_1+1}, l]}) = 0,$$

and for $1 \leq k \leq h_1 - 1$, we have

$$s_p((x - y)_{(\beta_k, \alpha_{k+1})}) + s_p((y)_{(\beta_k, \alpha_{k+1})}) - s_p((x)_{(\beta_k, \alpha_{k+1})}) = 0.$$

Furthermore, by Equation (10) and Corollary 4, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & s_p(x - y) + s_p(y) - s_p(x) \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{h_1} \left(s_p((x - y)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) + s_p((y)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) - s_p((x)_{[\alpha_k, \beta_k]}) \right) \\
 &= (p - 1) \sum_{k=1}^{h_1} (\beta_k - \alpha_k) = (p - 1) \delta_p(x, y).
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Proof of Corollary 1. Since $v_p(n!) = \frac{n - s_p(n)}{p - 1}$, by Theorem 1 we have

$$v_p\left(\frac{x!}{y!(x - y)!}\right) = \frac{1}{p - 1} (s_p(x - y) + s_p(y) - s_p(x)) = \delta_p(x, y).$$

This completes the proof. □

Proof of Theorem 2. Since $C_n(m) = \binom{n+m}{2m}((n-m)!)^2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} v_p(C_n(m)) &= v_p\left(\binom{n+m}{2m}\right) + 2v_p((n-m)!) \\ &= \frac{2}{p-1}(n-m-s_p(n-m)) + \delta_p(n+m, 2m). \end{aligned}$$

The proof is done. □

Lemma 4 ([2]). *For any positive integer n and prime p , we have*

$$\frac{n}{p-1} - \frac{\log(1+n)}{\log p} \leq v_p(n!) \leq \frac{n}{p-1}.$$

Lemma 5. *For any positive integer n and prime p , we have $s_p(n) \leq (p-1)\log_p(n+1)$.*

Proof. By Legendre’s formula and Lemma 4, we have

$$s_p(n) = n - (p-1)v_p(n!) \leq (p-1)\log_p(n+1).$$

□

Proof of Corollary 2. By Theorem 2, we have

$$\frac{p-1}{2n}v_p(C_n(m)) = 1 + \frac{p-1}{2n}\delta_p(n+m, 2m) - \frac{1}{n}(m+s_p(n-m)). \tag{11}$$

Observe that

$$0 \leq \delta_p(x, y) \leq \sum_{k=1}^l k = \frac{l(l+1)}{2} \leq \frac{\log_p^2 x + \log_p x}{2}.$$

Then

$$0 \leq \frac{p-1}{2n}\delta_p(n+m, 2m) \leq \frac{(p-1)(\log_p^2 n + \log_p n)}{4n}. \tag{12}$$

By Lemma 5, we have

$$0 \leq \frac{s_p(n-m)}{n} \leq \frac{(p-1)\log_p(n+1)}{n}. \tag{13}$$

Thus, by Equations (12) and (13), the limits of $\frac{p-1}{2n}\delta_p(n+m, 2m)$ and $\frac{1}{n}(m+s_p(n-m))$ in Equation (11) are both 0 as n goes to infinity. The proof is done. □

3. $m = 1$

The following formula of $v_p(C_n(1))$ was provided by Hong and Liu [11]:

$$v_p(C_n(1)) = \begin{cases} 2n - 2 - 2s_2(\frac{n-1}{2}) + v_2(\frac{n+1}{2}), & p = 2, 2 \nmid n; \\ 2n - 4 - 2s_2(\frac{n}{2} - 1) + v_2(\frac{n}{2}), & p = 2, 2 \mid n; \\ \frac{2}{p-1}(n - 1 - s_p(n - 1)) + v_p(n) + v_p(n + 1), & p > 2. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

By Theorem 2, for $n \geq 2$, we have

$$v_p(C_n(1)) = \frac{2}{p - 1}(n - 1 - s_p(n - 1)) + \delta_p(n + 1, 2). \quad (15)$$

For $p = 2$, we have

$$n + 1 = a_0 + a_1 \cdot 2 + a_2 \cdot 2^2 + \dots + a_l \cdot 2^l,$$

where $a_i = 0$ or 1 for $i = 0, 1, \dots, l$. Let $k = \min\{i \mid a_i = 1, i = 2, 3, \dots, l\}$.

If $a_1 = 1$, we have

$$n - 1 = a_0 + a_k \cdot 2^k + \dots + a_l \cdot 2^l.$$

It follows that $I' = \emptyset$ and $J' = \emptyset$. Hence, we have $\delta_2(n + 1, 2) = 0$ and $v_2(C_n(1)) = 2n - 2 - 2s_2(n - 1)$.

If $a_1 = 0$, we have

$$n - 1 = a_0 - 2 + a_k \cdot 2^k + \dots + a_l \cdot 2^l.$$

Then $I' = \{1\}$, $J' = \{k\}$, and $\delta_2(n + 1, 2) = k - 1$. Thus $v_2(C_n(1)) = 2n - 3 - 2s_2(n - 1) + k$.

For an odd prime p , by Corollary 1, we have

$$\delta_p(n + 1, 2) = v_p(\binom{n+1}{2}) = v_p(n) + v_p(n + 1).$$

Hence, we have $v_p(C_n(1)) = v_p(n) + v_p(n + 1) + \frac{2}{p-1}(n - 1 - s_p(n - 1))$.

In summary, Equation (15) is equivalent to

$$v_p(C_n(1)) = \begin{cases} 2n - 2 - 2s_2(n - 1), & p = 2, a_1 = 1; \\ 2n - 3 - 2s_2(n - 1) + k, & p = 2, a_1 = 0; \\ \frac{2}{p-1}(n - 1 - s_p(n - 1)) + v_p(n) + v_p(n + 1), & p > 2. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Herein, it is trivial to see that Equations (14) and (16) coincide with each other.

4. $m = 2$

In this section, we discuss the case for $m = 2$ and prove Theorem 3, while assuming $n \geq 3$. The objective is to show that a prime p exists such that $v_p(C_n(2))$ is odd. Let $S = \{a^2 \mid a \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. Let $\mathcal{P}(n)$ denote the set of primes p such that $v_p(n)$ is odd.

Lemma 6. *For a positive integer n and a prime $p \geq 5$, we have $v_p(\prod_{i=-1}^2(n+i)) = v_p(n+i_0)$ for some $i_0 \in \{-1, 0, 1, 2\}$.*

Proof. The greatest common divisors of any two numbers in $\{n-1, n, n+1, n+2\}$ should not exceed 3. If $p \nmid n+i$ for each i , then $v_p(\prod_{i=-1}^2(n+i)) = 0$. Otherwise, there exists a unique i_0 such that $p \mid n+i_0$. It follows that

$$v_p((n-1)n(n+1)(n+2)) = v_p(n+i_0). \quad \square$$

Proof of Theorem 3. By Theorem 2, we observe that $v_p(C_n(2))$ and $\delta_p(n+2, 4)$ have the same parity. By Corollary 1, we have

$$\delta_p(n+2, 4) = v_p\left(\binom{n+2}{4}\right) = v_p((n^2-1)(n^2+2n)) - 3v_p(2) - v_p(3).$$

We assume that $v_p\left(\binom{n+2}{4}\right)$ is even for all primes $p \geq 5$. Otherwise, there exists a prime $p \geq 5$ such that $v_p(C_n(2))$ is odd and $C_n(2)$ is not a square. Thus, this assumption and Lemma 6 imply that $p \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2-1)$ if $p \geq 5$. Similarly, $\mathcal{P}(n^2+2n) \neq \emptyset$ and $p \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2+2n)$ if $p \geq 5$. Thus, for any $p \geq 5$, we have

$$p \notin P(n-1) \cup P(n) \cup P(n+1) \cup P(n+2). \quad (17)$$

Case 1. $\mathcal{P}(n^2-1) = \{3\}$. If $3 \in \mathcal{P}(n^2+2n)$, then $v_3\left(\binom{n+2}{4}\right) = v_3(n^2+2n) + v_3(n^2-1) - 1$ is odd. Thus $C_n(2)$ is not a square. If $\mathcal{P}(n^2+2n) = \{2\}$, then n is even. Hence $(n, n+2) = 2$. Since $\frac{n^2+2n}{2} \in S$, we either have $n \in S$ or $n+2 \in S$. Thus $n+1, n-1 \notin S$, which contradicts $\frac{n^2-1}{3} \in S$.

Case 2. $\mathcal{P}(n^2-1) = \{2\}$. In this case, we have that n is odd and $(n+1, n-1) = 2$. Since $\frac{n^2-1}{2} \in S$, we either have $n+1 \in S$ or $n-1 \in S$. Thus $n, n+2 \notin S$, which implies that $\mathcal{P}(n), \mathcal{P}(n+2) \neq \emptyset$. If $2 \notin \mathcal{P}(n) \cup \mathcal{P}(n+2)$ and $\mathcal{P}(n) \cap \mathcal{P}(n+2) = \emptyset$, then there exists a prime $p \geq 5$ in $\mathcal{P}(n) \cup \mathcal{P}(n+2)$, which contradicts Equation (17).

Case 3. $\mathcal{P}(n^2-1) = \{2, 3\}$. In this case, we have that n is odd and $(n, n+2) = 1$. Since $n^2+2n \notin S$, we either have $n \notin S$ or $n+2 \notin S$. Since $2 \mid n^2-1$ and $3 \mid n^2-1$, we have $2, 3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n)$. Thus, combining with Equation (17), we have $n \in S$ and $n+2 \notin S$. Since $2 \notin \mathcal{P}(n+2)$, we have $\mathcal{P}(n+2) = \{3\}$. Thus

$$v_3\left(\binom{n+2}{4}\right) = v_3(n+2) + v_3(n^2-1) - 1$$

is odd.

The proof of Theorem 3 is completed. □

5. $m = 3$

Similar to Section 4, we discuss the proof for Theorem 4 in this section.

Lemma 7. *For a positive integer n and a prime $p \geq 7$, we have $v_p(\prod_{i=-2}^3(n+i)) = v_p(n + i_0)$ for some $i_0 \in [-2, 3]$.*

Proof. The proof is similarly to that of Lemma 6. □

Lemma 8. *The following facts have been established.*

1. *The Diophantine equation $x^2 - y^2 = k$ has no solutions when $x > 3$ and $1 \leq k \leq 5$.*
2. *The Diophantine equation $ax^2 - 2y^2 = k$ has no solutions when x and y are odd, $a \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, and $k \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.*
3. *The Diophantine equation $ax^2 - ky^2 = -1$ has no solutions when x is odd and y is even for any integer k and $a \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.*
4. *The Diophantine equation $x^2 - 5y^2 = k$ has no solutions for $k \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$.*

Proof. Here, the first statement is trivial. For the other statements, otherwise, we have $-2 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, $-1 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, or $x^2 \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$, respectively, which are all contradictions. □

Lemma 9. *For an integer $n > 6$, there exists at most one square in $\{n - 2, n - 1, n, n + 1, n + 2, n + 3\}$.*

Proof. By trivial computations, we observe that the lemma holds for $n = 7, 8, 9$, and 10. When $n > 10$, we assume that $n + i, n + j$ are squares when $i > j$ and $i, j \in \{-2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3\}$. It follows that $(\sqrt{n+i}, \sqrt{n+j})$ is a solution to $x^2 - y^2 = i - j$ with $\sqrt{n+i} > 3$ and $1 \leq i - j \leq 5$. This result contradicts the first statement of Lemma 8. □

Proof of Theorem 4. Upon the decompositions of $C_n(3)$ when $n = 4, 5$, and 6, the theorem holds trivially for $n \leq 6$. Hence, we have assumed $n > 6$.

By Theorem 2, it is sufficient to prove that there exists a prime p such that $v_p(\binom{n+3}{6})$ is odd. By Corollary 1, we have

$$v_p(\binom{n+3}{6}) = v_p(n^2 - 4) + v_p(n^2 - 1) + v_p(n^2 + 3n) - v_p(5) - 2v_p(12). \tag{18}$$

By Lemma 7, if there exists a prime $p \geq 7$ in $\bigcup_{i=-2}^3 \mathcal{P}(n+i)$, then $v_p(\binom{n+3}{6})$ is odd, and $C_n(3)$ is not a square. Hence, we always assume $\bigcup_{i=-2}^3 \mathcal{P}(n+i) \subseteq \{2, 3, 5\}$.

We claim that $n^2 - 1 \notin S, n^2 - 4 \notin S$, and $n^2 + 3n \notin S$. The first two facts are trivial, while for the last fact, observe that $(n, n + 3) = 1$ or 3. Thus $n^2 + 3n \in S$

implies that either $n, n + 3 \in S$ or $\frac{n}{3}, \frac{n+3}{3} \in S$. This yields a solution $(\sqrt{n+3}, \sqrt{n})$ or $(\sqrt{\frac{n+3}{3}}, \sqrt{\frac{n}{3}})$ of $x^2 - y^2 = 3$ or $x^2 - y^2 = 1$, respectively, which contradicts Lemma 8.

Case 1. $\mathcal{P}(n^2 - 4) = \{5\}$. Since $n^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$, we have $5 \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2 - 1)$. If $3 \in \mathcal{P}(n^2 - 1)$, then $v_3\left(\binom{n+3}{6}\right) = v_3(n^2 - 1) + v_3(n^2 - 4) - 2$ is odd as desired. If $\mathcal{P}(n^2 - 1) = \{2\}$, then n is odd and $(n + 1, n - 1) = 2$. Since $\frac{n^2-1}{2} \in S$, we either have $n + 1 \in S$ or $n - 1 \in S$. Thus $n + 2, n - 2 \notin S$. Therefore, by the fact that $(n + 2, n - 2) = 1$, we have $\frac{n^2-4}{5} \notin S$, which contradicts $\mathcal{P}(n^2 - 4) = \{5\}$.

Case 2. $\mathcal{P}(n^2 - 4) = \{3\}$. Since $n^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{3}$, we have $\mathcal{P}(n) \cap \mathcal{P}(n + 3) = \emptyset$ and $3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n) \cup \mathcal{P}(n + 3)$.

Case 2.1. $n \notin S, n + 3 \notin S$. If $\mathcal{P}(n) = \{5\}$ and $\mathcal{P}(n + 3) = \{2\}$, then n is odd and $(n + 2, n - 2) = 1$. It follows that either $n + 2 \in S$ or $n - 2 \in S$ since $\frac{n^2-4}{3} \in S$. Therefore, we either have a solution $(\sqrt{n+2}, \sqrt{\frac{n}{5}})$ of $x^2 - 5y^2 = 2$ or a solution $(\sqrt{n-2}, \sqrt{\frac{n}{5}})$ of $x^2 - 5y^2 = -2$, which is a contradiction. Thus $\mathcal{P}(n) = \{2\}$ and $v_2(n)$ is odd. Additionally, since $2 \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2 - 4)$, we observe that $v_2(n^2 - 4)$ is even. It follows that $v_2\left(\binom{n+3}{6}\right) = v_2(n) + v_2(n^2 - 4) - 4$ is odd.

Case 2.2. $n \in S$ or $n + 3 \in S$. In this case, we have $n + 2 \notin S$ and $n - 2 \notin S$. If n is odd, then $(n + 2, n - 2) = 1$. Since $\frac{n^2-4}{3} \in S$, we either have $n + 2 \in S$ or $n - 2 \in S$, which is a contradiction. Hence n is even. If $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, then $(\frac{n+2}{4}, \frac{n-2}{4}) = 1$. Since $\frac{n^2-4}{3} \in S$, we have $n + 2 \in S$ or $n - 2 \in S$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, we have $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ and $(\frac{n+2}{2}, \frac{n-2}{2}) = 1$. Thus, either $\frac{n-2}{2} \in S$ or $\frac{n+2}{2} \in S$ since $\frac{n^2-4}{3} \in S$.

If $n \in S$, then $\mathcal{P}(n + 3) = \{5\}$ since $2 \notin \mathcal{P}(n + 3)$. Therefore $\frac{n+3}{5} \in S$. Hence, we either have an odd solution $(\sqrt{\frac{n+3}{5}}, \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{2}})$ of $5x^2 - 2y^2 = 5$ or an odd solution $(\sqrt{\frac{n+3}{5}}, \sqrt{\frac{n+2}{2}})$ of $5x^2 - 2y^2 = 1$, which is a contradiction.

Additionally, if $n + 3 \in S$, then we either have an odd solution $(\sqrt{n+3}, \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{2}})$ of $x^2 - 2y^2 = 5$ or an odd solution $(\sqrt{n+3}, \sqrt{\frac{n+2}{2}})$ of $x^2 - 2y^2 = 1$, which is a contradiction.

Case 3. $\mathcal{P}(n^2 - 4) = \{2\}$. In this case, we have that n is even. If $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, we have $v_2(n^2 - 4) = 2$, which implies that $2 \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2 - 4)$. Therefore $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ and $(\frac{n-2}{4}, \frac{n+2}{4}) = 1$. Since $\frac{n^2-4}{2} \in S$, we either have $n - 2 \in S$ or $n + 2 \in S$. Thus $n - 1, n + 1, n + 3 \notin S$, and $\mathcal{P}(n - 1), \mathcal{P}(n + 1)$ and $\mathcal{P}(n + 3)$ are all non-empty sets. Since any two of $n - 1, n + 1$, and $n + 3$ are coprime, we have that $\mathcal{P}(n - 1), \mathcal{P}(n + 1)$, and $\mathcal{P}(n + 3)$ are disjoint from each other. Therefore, one of $\mathcal{P}(n - 1), \mathcal{P}(n + 1)$, and $\mathcal{P}(n + 3)$ contains 2, which contradicts that n is even.

Case 4. $\mathcal{P}(n^2 - 4) = \{3, 5\}$. In this case, we have $n^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{3}$ and $n^2 \equiv 4$

(mod 5). It follows that $3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n) \cup \mathcal{P}(n+3)$ and $5 \notin \bigcup_{i=-1}^1 \mathcal{P}(n+i)$. Additionally, we have $\mathcal{P}(n) \cap \mathcal{P}(n+3) = \emptyset$ since $(n, n+3) = 1$.

If either $n-1 \in S$ or $n+1 \in S$, then we have $n \notin S$ and $n+3 \notin S$. Thus $\mathcal{P}(n) = \{2\}$, which implies that n is even. Hence, we have $\mathcal{P}(n+3) = \{5\}$ since $2, 3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n+3)$. It follows that $v_5(n^2-4)$ and $v_5(n+3)$ are both odd. Thus $v_5\left(\binom{n+3}{6}\right) = v_5(n^2-4) + v_5(n+3) - 1$ is odd as desired.

If $n-1, n+1 \notin S$, then we have that $\mathcal{P}(n^2-1) \neq \{2\}$. Otherwise, we have that n is odd and $\frac{n^2-1}{2} \in S$, which implies that either $n-1 \in S$ or $n+1 \in S$. If $\mathcal{P}(n^2-1) = \{2, 3\}$, then n is odd and $\frac{n^2-1}{6} \in S$. Hence, we obtain a solution $(\sqrt{\frac{n^2-4}{15}}, \sqrt{\frac{n^2-1}{6}})$ of $5x^2 - 2y^2 = -1$, where x is odd and y is even. This is a contradiction. If $\mathcal{P}(n^2-1) = \{3\}$, then $\frac{n^2-1}{3} \in S$. Hence, we claim that n is odd. Otherwise, we have $(n+1, n-1) = 1$, which implies that either $n-1 \in S$ or $n+1 \in S$. Hence, we get a solution $(\sqrt{\frac{n^2-4}{15}}, \sqrt{\frac{n^2-1}{3}})$ of $5x^2 - y^2 = -1$, where x is odd and y is even. This is also a contradiction.

Case 5. $\mathcal{P}(n^2-4) = \{2, 5\}$. In this case, we have that n is even and $n^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$. It follows that $2, 5 \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2-1)$. Therefore $\mathcal{P}(n^2-1) = \{3\}$ and $3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2+3n)$. We have $v_3\left(\binom{n+3}{6}\right) \equiv v_3(n^2-1) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Hence $v_3\left(\binom{n+3}{6}\right)$ is odd as desired.

Case 6. $\mathcal{P}(n^2-4) = \{2, 3\}$. In this case, we have that n is even and $n^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. It follows that $3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n)$, and $2, 3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n+3)$. Since $2 \in \mathcal{P}(n^2-4)$, we have $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. Therefore $(n-2, n+2) = 4$.

Case 6.1. $n-1 \in S$ or $n+1 \in S$. In this case, we have $n \notin S$ and $n+3 \notin S$. Hence $\mathcal{P}(n+3) = \{5\}$ and $5 \notin \mathcal{P}(n)$. Therefore $\mathcal{P}(n) = \{2\}$ since $3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n)$. Since $\frac{n^2-4}{6} \in S$, we have $\frac{n^2-4}{6 \cdot 16} \in S$, which implies that $\frac{n-2}{8} \in S$ or $\frac{n+2}{8} \in S$ since $\frac{n-2}{4}, \frac{n+2}{4} \notin S$ and $\left(\frac{n-2}{4}, \frac{n+2}{4}\right) = 1$. Thus we either have $\frac{n-2}{2} \in S$ or $\frac{n+2}{2} \in S$. Hence, we get a solution $(\sqrt{\frac{n}{2}}, \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{2}})$ or $(\sqrt{\frac{n+2}{2}}, \sqrt{\frac{n}{2}})$ of $x^2 - y^2 = 1$, which is a contradiction.

Case 6.2. $n-1 \notin S, n+1 \notin S$. Since $\mathcal{P}(n-1) \cap \mathcal{P}(n+1) = \emptyset$ and $2 \notin \mathcal{P}(n-1) \cup \mathcal{P}(n+1)$, we either have $\mathcal{P}(n-1) = \{3\}, \mathcal{P}(n+1) = \{5\}$ or $\mathcal{P}(n-1) = \{5\}, \mathcal{P}(n+1) = \{3\}$. Since $(n-1, n+1) = 1$, we have $\mathcal{P}(n^2-1) = \mathcal{P}(n-1) \cup \mathcal{P}(n+1)$. Thus $5 \in \mathcal{P}(n^2-1)$ and $n^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, which implies that $5 \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2+3n)$. Since $3 \nmid n$, we also have $3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2+3n)$. Hence $\mathcal{P}(n^2+3n) = \{2\}$ and $\frac{n^2+3n}{2} \in S$. It follows that $\frac{n}{2} \in S$ and $n+3 \in S$ since $\left(\frac{n}{2}, n+3\right) = 1$. Therefore, we have $n-2 \notin S$ and $n+2 \notin S$. By the same argument on $\frac{n^2-4}{6}$ in Case 6.1, we either have $\frac{n-2}{2} \in S$ or $\frac{n+2}{2} \in S$. Therefore, we get a solution $(\sqrt{\frac{n}{2}}, \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{2}})$ or $(\sqrt{\frac{n+2}{2}}, \sqrt{\frac{n}{2}})$ of $x^2 - y^2 = 1$, which is also a contradiction.

Case 7. $\mathcal{P}(n^2-4) = \{2, 3, 5\}$. In this case, we have that n is even, $n^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{3}$, and $n^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$. It follows that $2, 5 \notin \mathcal{P}(n^2-1)$, which implies that

$\mathcal{P}(n^2 - 1) = \{3\}$. Therefore, either $n - 1 \in S$ or $n + 1 \in S$ since $(n - 1, n + 1) = 1$. Hence, we have $n \notin S$ and $n + 3 \notin S$. Since $3, 5 \notin \mathcal{P}(n)$, we have $\mathcal{P}(n) = \{2\}$, which implies that $\mathcal{P}(n + 3) = \{5\}$ since $3 \notin \mathcal{P}(n + 3)$ and $(n, n + 3) = 1$. Therefore $v_5\left(\binom{n+3}{6}\right) = v_5(n^2 - 4) + v_5(n + 3) - 1$ is odd.

The proof of Theorem 4 is completed. □

6. Criterion for $C_n(m)$ Being a Powerful Number

The criterion for $C_n(m)$ being a powerful number has been discussed in this section. A relevant example has also been provided to conclude the findings.

Theorem 5. *Let m, n be positive integers with $n \geq m + 1$. If there are no primes in $(n - m, n + m]$, then $C_n(m)$ is a powerful number.*

Proof. Recall that

$$v_p(C_n(m)) = 2v_p((n - m)!) + v_p\left(\binom{n+m}{2m}\right). \tag{19}$$

If there are no primes in $(n - m, n + m]$, then for any prime divisor p of $C_n(m)$, we have $p \leq n - m$, which implies that $p|(n - m)!$. By Equation (19), we have $v_p(C_n(m)) \geq 2v_p((n - m)!) \geq 2$. Thus $C_n(m)$ is a powerful number. □

Corollary 5. *Let m, n be positive integers with $n \geq 3m$. Then $C_n(m)$ is a powerful number if and only if there are no primes in $(n - m, n + m]$.*

Proof. By Theorem 5, the sufficiency has been established. Conversely, assume that there exists a prime $p \in (n - m, n + m]$. Since $p > n - m \geq 2m$, we have $v_p((n - m)!) = 0$ and $v_p((2m)!) = 0$. Hence $v_p\left(\binom{n+m}{2m}\right) = 0$. Let $p = n + i$ for some $i \in (-m, m]$. Since the greatest common divisors of any two numbers in $\{n - m + 1, n - m + 2, \dots, n + m\}$ should not exceed $2m - 1$, we have $p \nmid n + j$ for $j \neq i, j \in (-m, m]$. Thus, by Equation (19) we have

$$v_p(C_n(m)) = \sum_{k=1-m}^m v_p(n + k) = v_p(n + i) = 1.$$

It follows that $C_n(m)$ is not a powerful number. □

Remark 1. From Corollary 5, it is easy to prove that if $C_{n_0}(m_0)$ is not a powerful number with $m_0 \leq \frac{n_0}{3}$, then $C_{n_0}(m)$ is not a powerful number for all $m \in (m_0, \frac{n_0}{3}]$.

Lemma 10 ([13]). *For every positive integer n , there exists a prime $p \in [n, \frac{9(n+3)}{8}]$.*

Corollary 6. *When $m \geq 3$, we have that $C_n(m)$ is not a powerful number if $n \in [\frac{5m+18}{4}, 17m - 36]$.*

Proof. Since $m \geq 3$, we have $\frac{5m+18}{4} \leq 3m$. Recall that

$$v_p(C_n(m)) = v_p((n - m)!) + v_p((2m + 1) \cdots (n + m)). \tag{20}$$

For $\frac{5m+18}{4} \leq n < 3m$, we have $n + m \geq \frac{9(2m+4)}{8}$. By Lemma 10, there exists a prime $p \in [2m + 1, n + m]$. Since $p \geq 2m + 1 > n - m$, we have $v_p((n - m)!) = 0$. Since the greatest common divisors of any two numbers in $\{2m + 1, 2m + 2, \dots, n + m\}$ should not exceed $2m - 1$, we also have $v_p((2m + 1) \cdots (n + m)) = 1$. Thus, by Equation (20) we have $v_p(C_n(m)) = 1$, which implies that $C_n(m)$ is not a powerful number for $n \in [\frac{5m+18}{4}, 3m)$.

For $3m \leq n \leq 17m - 36$, we have $\frac{9(n-m+4)}{8} \leq n + m$. By Lemma 10, there exists a prime $p \in [n - m + 1, n + m]$. Therefore, by Corollary 5, we have that $C_n(m)$ is not a powerful number. $\square$

Example 3. Let $n \leq 1000$. The following table lists N for $2 \leq m \leq 10$, where $N = \#\{n \in [m + 1, 1000] \mid C_n(m) \text{ is a powerful number}\}$.

m	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
N	402	219	124	60	28	10	6	2	0

Table 1: N for $2 \leq m \leq 10$.

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